

MS16

Living lab with fully operational DVC decision system ready for further exploitation

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Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** 30/06/2025
 - **Actual submission date:** 25/06/2025
 - **Project start date:** September 1st 2021
 - **Duration:** 48 months
 - **Work package:** WP6
 - **Work package leader:** JSI
 - **Milestone Title:** Living lab with fully operational DVC decision system ready for further exploitation
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- **Mean of Verification** Report confirming functionality and results.

1. Milestone description

In order to achieve the milestone "Living lab with fully operational DVC decision system ready for further exploitation", activities focussed on the completion, verification and improvement of the Market Avenue Generator (MAG) decision support system. MAG was developed as a digital, AI-supported decision support tool that guides users through the development of sustainable business models for underutilised crops (UCs). The system includes a Lean Canvas-based business modelling module, a technology readiness level (TRL) assessment module, a multidimensional sustainability assessment module (economic, environmental, social) and an insight module. AI-supported internal feedback is included in all modules and helps users to iteratively refine their business models by providing structured, real-time suggestions on content quality, coherence and completeness. In addition, an expert review option allows for external validation before embarking on the development of the full business plan. The system has been implemented as a freely accessible web-based tool (**MAG**) and is accompanied by a publicly available **user manual** containing guidance for first-time users and supporting organisations.

Activities performed: MAG builds on the earlier conceptual framework of WP6 and further develops the original four-tier approach into a five modular, AI-enhanced digital tool for the development of sustainable business models:

- **Artificial Intelligence (LLMs) in MAG**

An important innovation of the MAG system is the integration of a locale hosted Large Language Model (LLM), which provides real-time AI support for all modules of the platform. LLMs are advanced AI models that have been trained on large amounts of text data and are thus able to understand context, generate meaningful answers and help users structure their business models more effectively. MAG integrates Gemma 2, a state-of-the-art LLM with 27 billion parameters capable of processing complex business concepts, recognising patterns and providing tailored recommendations. Unlike static business modelling tools, this AI-driven system allows users to interact dynamically with

the platform, iteratively refining their ideas and ensuring that every component of their business model is well defined before moving forward.

The LLM plays a critical role in several modules of MAG by i) helping users understand key business modelling concepts and providing explanations for various components of the business model; ii) identifying inconsistencies or missing information in user inputs and suggesting improvements; iii) supports users in determining their Technology Readiness Level (TRL) by helping them assess the stage of development of their innovation; vi) offers contextualised recommendations based on industry benchmarks, market trends and sustainability considerations; v) generates initial comments and recommendations prior to validation by experts and helps refine business briefs prior to submission.

• Module 1 - Lean Canvas

The Lean Canvas module provides a structured entry point for defining and refining the core components of a business idea, such as the problem, the solution, the unique value proposition, the customer segments, and so on. Based on the Lean Canvas framework, the

module guides users through these eight sections. An integrated AI assistant provides real-time contextualised suggestions to improve logical consistency and strategic alignment. This iterative support helps users to better articulate their ideas before moving on to the more detailed business model development phase.

The screenshot displays the 'Lean Canvas' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'HOME', 'CANVAS', 'TRL', 'MODEL', 'SUSTAINABILITY', and 'INSIGHTS'. Below this is a grid of eight numbered sections: 1. Problem / Opportunity, 2. Unique Value Proposition, 3. Solution, 4. 'Jobs to be Done' advantage, 5. Channels and Channels, 6. Revenue Streams, 7. Key Metrics, 8. Cost Structure, and 9. Customer Segments. To the right of the grid, there is a 'STRUCTURE AND SIMPLICITY' section with a description of the Lean Canvas and a 'HIGH-LEVEL OVERVIEW' section. Below the grid, there is a 'SECTION SELECTION' dropdown menu. The main content area shows '1 PROBLEM / OPPORTUNITY' with instructions and a 'YOUR INPUT' field.

• Module 2 - Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) module supports users in assessing the technological maturity of their innovation. It guides them through a visual, nine-level scale, which is divided into four phases: Idea, Prototype, Validation and Production. Each stage comprises clearly formulated questions with explanatory notes. Based on user responses, the system determines the highest validated TRL. This makes it possible to compare the business concept with its technological feasibility, which is essential for realistic commercial planning.

• Module 3 - Business Model

Building on the Lean Canvas module, the Business Model module enables users to further develop their ideas and refine them into a comprehensive and structured business model. This module guides users through 11 strategic sections, including sections such as market positioning, operational planning, finance, risk management, etc. The integrated AI assistant provides contextualised suggestions and identifies gaps or inconsistencies, helping users to iteratively improve the quality and consistency of their input. This step is important to prepare the business model for expert review and future development of the business plan.

• Module 1 - Sustainability Assessment

With this module, users can assess the sustainability performance of their company in terms of economic, environmental and social dimensions. The assessment is carried out at specific nodes in the value chain - such as production, processing, transport and market - depending on the scope of the company. For each selected node, users enter structured inputs based on predefined qualitative indicators that are aligned with established sustainability frameworks. The system then aggregates the results and visualises them using a colour-coded scale

(green – high, orange – medium, red – low) so that users can clearly identify strengths and areas for improvement. The AI assistant supports users in entering data by providing information, detecting missing or inconsistent inputs and ensuring completeness. The results of the assessment are automatically integrated into the annual report to ensure that sustainability is embedded as a key dimension of the overall business model.

• Module 5 - Insights

The Insights module offers an internal AI-based validation of the entire business model. It consolidates the input from all previous modules and generates a diagnostic report with targeted comments and recommendations. This includes feedback on missing elements, inconsistencies and coherence gaps. The AI acts as a virtual reviewer and allows users to iteratively refine their business model until they feel they have considered all relevant aspects and require further support from an external expert. This ensures that the expert review can focus on strategic validation while the user has already maximised the quality and completeness of their submission.

2. Mean of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA?

Yes: The MAG system was verified through internal validation and practical stakeholder testing.

- **Internal testing and documentation**

During the development of the MAG tool, draft business models were created in T6.4 for selected Aurora farms using early components such as Lean Canvas templates and structured sustainability inputs. The feedback and insights from these cases fed directly into the structure and logic of the tool, ensuring that it aligned with the real needs of agri-food innovation. This first-stage validation played a key role in the further development and testing of the system.

Building on this foundation, the fully developed MAG system underwent a comprehensive internal review by the technical development team. As part of the broader living lab process, this included checking the functionality of all five modules (Lean Canvas, TRL, Business model, Sustainability assessment and Insights), testing cross-platform compatibility and validating the data flow and integration between the modules. A key focus of the internal testing process was the AI-supported feedback system, which had to provide reliable, real-time suggestions and maintain quality control throughout the user workflow. This process was supported by insights from the development of business models for Aurora farms, which served as calibration cases to

test and adjust the accuracy and clarity of AI-generated suggestions across different modules.

- **Stakeholder validation through the CREATOR Workshop**

To ensure that the MAG system is functional, user-friendly and practical for the target groups, the final version was tested and reviewed during the **CREATOR workshop** organised by Jozef Stefan Institute in April 2025. The aim of the

workshop was to validate the tool's performance in a realistic environment and gather structured user feedback to make the final refinements before wider dissemination. This was the central Living Lab integration event. The event brought together 15 participants selected to represent three main categories of stakeholders: (i) end-users, including farmers and agri-food entrepreneurs working with underutilised crops; (ii) innovation and advisory service providers; and (iii) support organisations such as rural development agencies and policy-related institutions.

The workshop was divided into three parts: (1) a brief introduction to the MAG system, its purpose and modules; (2) a practical session in which participants were invited to use the tool individually to develop a simplified business model; and (3) a structured evaluation phase with questionnaires and facilitated discussion. Participants worked directly with all five modules of the MAG tool — Lean Canvas, TRL assessment, Business model, Sustainability assessment and Insight — providing comprehensive feedback on user guidance and content logic.

Feedback was gathered via a prepared form and an oral group discussion, focussing on the key dimensions of usability: ease of navigation, clarity of instructions, logical flow of steps, usefulness of AI guidance and relevance of sustainability indicators. The results showed a high level of satisfaction among users, with most participants rating the tool favourably in terms of structure and completeness.

Some constructive suggestions were also made, particularly in relation to the terminology used in the sustainability module, the need for clearer instructions in the TRL module, the language of the system (English only) and the overall visual hierarchy between input and feedback sections.

Based on these suggestions, several targeted updates were made before the final release of the tool. These included clearer and more user-friendly terminology, improved navigation logic to support a smoother flow between modules, contextualised guidance within the tool (e.g. tooltips and help icons), and visual adjustments to improve user orientation and overall usability. The CREATOR workshop was therefore important not only to test the functionality and completeness of MAG, but also to validate its accessibility, relevance and effectiveness for the different user groups involved in agri-food innovation.

Once all components of the system were confirmed to be operational and ready for further use and exploitation, we wrote the **User manual**, which guides users through the MAG's functionality features.

3. Conclusions

The **User manual**, **CREATOR Workshop report** and **Deliverable D6.3** are the main documents confirming that the **MAG** fulfils all expected and promised technical and practical requirements.

The tool will officially launch at the upcoming "AI for Nature-Based Innovation" workshop in Porto (**ipnc2025**), which is expected to attract over 90 participants from all over Europe. This event is an important opportunity for broader exploitation and outreach, as well as for gathering additional feedback from agri-food innovators, researchers and policy stakeholders to support further development of the **MAG**.

The evidence provided in this document proves that we successfully achieved all milestone requirements.